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'Flexible' versus 'fragmented' authoritarianism: evidence from Chinese foreign policy during the Xi Jinping era

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ABSTRACT

Since the 1980s, a widely held view within the scholarly literature has been that China's political system is characterised by 'fragmented authoritarianism' (FA). According to the FA model, the central government's power is limited by competing interests among a diversity of actors within the Chinese state. These actors include central government ministries and bureaucracies, local governments, and corporations, which bargain for influence over policy direction, leading to incoherence and inconsistency in decision-making. In this paper, we aim to demonstrate that the FA framework is misleading in the realm of foreign policy, especially in the era of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). In its place, we characterise China's decision-making and policy implementation system as *flexible authoritarianism*. Although actors such as corporations and local governments have a considerable degree of autonomy, they are responsible primarily for policy implementation, to which they can make adjustments within a set of broadly defined boundaries. Long-term strategic goals defined by the Party leadership are combined with elements of neoliberal free-market economics and applied with a remarkable degree of consistency. We illustrate the argument through evidence and case studies from Chinese foreign policy during the BRI era.

KEYWORDS

China; foreign policy; fragmented authoritarianism; flexible authoritarianism; Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)

Introduction

Beginning with seminal publications by Lieberthal and Oksenberg (1988) and Lieberthal and Lampton (1992), the claim that the Chinese system can be characterised as 'fragmented authoritarianism' has dominated academic studies of China's governance system. This model emphasises middle-up processes as the key drivers of decision-making, where mid-level bureaucracies engage in extensive bargaining with both higher authorities and local actors. While top-down processes are present, they are considered less determinative, as central policies are often subject to negotiation and adaptation at lower levels, resulting in a fragmented and complex governance structure. Since then,

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the fragmented authoritarianism model has been updated. For example, Mertha (2009) includes non-state actors, such as NGOs, private sector entities, and even individuals in this fragmentation formulation. One of the most recent versions of fragmented authoritarianism emanates from two publications by Lee Jones and Shahar Hameiri (Hameiri and Jones 2016; Jones and Hameiri 2021), who connect fragmented authoritarianism to what they call ‘state transformation’. This is the idea that states in general, and China in particular, are becoming decentralised so that governance is contested by a wide range of actors: consequently, the central government is not in full control of foreign policy.

While supporting the notion that all modern states are subject to a degree of state transformation within the global neoliberal system of free market capitalism, we posit that the notion that the People’s Republic of China (PRC) has a fragmented political system and fragmented foreign policy is misleading. The term ‘fragmented authoritarianism’ generates an inaccurate image of uncoordinated, dysfunctional, and incoherent decision-making. It depicts a China in which governance structures are chaotic and capable of being contested by individuals and interest groups. Instead, we propose that what some scholars have called ‘fragmented authoritarianism’ should be reinterpreted as a mistaken interpretation of ‘crossing the river by feeling the stones’—a policy of trial-and-error under Deng Xiaoping in which local actors were permitted a considerable degree of freedom to experiment with new methods of economic development (Shambaugh 2021, 141). This was especially the case during the 1980s, 1990s, and 2000s, when the Chinese economy was expanding rapidly from a low base and the government provided a more permissive environment for businesses to be entrepreneurial in the service of profit-making and state-building processes. As China’s economic growth has slowed, central control has hardened under Xi Jinping, revealing the absence of full-scale ‘fragmentation’ in the sense in which adherents of Western free market economics and democratic politics would intend.

Instead, we propose that the Chinese governance system should be recategorized as what Anna Schwenck (2024), in a study of contemporary Russia, calls ‘flexible authoritarianism’. Schwenck applies the term to the Russian government’s top-down use of selected aspects of neoliberal economics to persuade citizens and other actors to buy into its agendas and maintain its support base. Instead of Schwenck’s emphasis on consensus building in society, we focus primarily on how the Chinese government implements foreign policy in the service of national strategic goals. We broaden the term *flexible authoritarianism* to refer to the use of agents of the state such as companies and the military to achieve broad, long-term strategic goals by granting actors a considerable degree of autonomous decision-making in policy implementation.

In the realm of foreign policy, under Xi Jinping, the Chinese government’s strategic goals have been subsumed into the overarching framework of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). The BRI serves as a broad, flexible envelope within which actors such as state-owned enterprises (SOEs) and private companies can pursue profit-making activities as long as they adhere to the state’s strategic goals (Garlick 2024). As agents of the state, they are granted a considerable degree of autonomy to make decisions, but only as long as outcomes promote the state’s strategic goals alongside the individual actors’ own interests. If they do not, individuals may be sanctioned and actors may be replaced. Profit-seeking is seen as a driver of economic growth in the foreign policy sphere as in the

domestic, but only as long as leading individuals in companies do not go too far in seeking to line their own pockets, failing to follow through on promises, or damaging China's image overseas.

Actors are given a degree of independence to implement government policy, but their actions must always remain in line with the state's overarching goals: we characterise these unwritten rules as the *bounds of the permissible*. This means that actors who step out of line with what the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) sees as national priorities are removed, replaced, or given warnings. Their activities are monitored through oversight mechanisms such as reporting systems and the placement of high-ranked Party officials in leading positions (Lee 2017, 6; Nee and Oppen 2007, 118–21). Thus, we posit that the persistent use of *fragmented* authoritarianism to understand the Chinese political economy is a mistaken interpretation: instead, today's decision-making structures in China can be characterised as *flexible* authoritarianism. In essence, the state prioritises maintaining a high degree of control while allowing actors a degree of autonomous action to achieve long-term strategic goals within the unwritten bounds of the permissible.

In this article we present some case studies to offer a counter-narrative to fragmented authoritarianism. These emphasise the party-centric governance and flexible dynamics within the Chinese state that the FA model overlooks. The value of introducing the flexible authoritarianism model lies in its ability to reconcile the apparent contradictions within China's governance system—between centralisation and decentralisation, coherence and inconsistency, control and autonomy. While previous models have contributed important insights into various facets of China's governance, they often fail to account for the sophisticated balance that the CCP strikes between maintaining centralised strategic control and delegating operational autonomy within prescribed limits. Flexible authoritarianism moves beyond the dichotomy of centralisation versus fragmentation, presenting a nuanced understanding of how China achieves long-term strategic goals while remaining adaptable to changing circumstances, particularly in the era of Xi's BRI. Developing the concept in this way contributes also to the literature on authoritarianism in general. While enabling a clearer understanding of Xi's China, the model may thus also potentially be applied to other authoritarian regimes pursuing strategies which fall on the spectrum between fragmentation and centralisation.

The article is structured as follows. First, we discuss the FA model, pointing out the problems inherent in it. Then we move on to present flexible authoritarianism. Finally, we support our argument through several case studies documenting Chinese foreign policy initiatives in the era of the BRI.

Origins of the fragmented authoritarianism model

Over the past four decades, FA has been the prevailing conceptual model for understanding Chinese political system in western academic and policy circles (Brødsgaard 2016; Landry 2008; Lieberthal and Oksenberg 1988; Mertha 2009; 2024; Shirk 2018; Tubilewicz 2024; Zeng 2020). The influence of the FA model also extends beyond the field of China studies. For instance, it has been used by IR scholars, notably Hameiri and Jones (2016) and Jones and Hameiri (2021), to argue that far from being a monolithic or unitary actor, the Chinese political system is riven by fragmentation and, as a result,

China's international behaviour is the product of chaotic internal power struggles and policy inconsistencies rather than a coherent national strategy. While some sources (Ahlers 2018; Naughton 2018; Shambaugh 2021) have recognised the phenomenon of increasing centralisation and its impacts on governance during the Xi Jinping era of Chinese politics, it has not been conceptualised or presented as a to counter FA in scholarly literature to any great extent. Such discussions are largely absent in the academic literature on China's foreign policy and behaviour in international relations where FA has been actively promoted in recent years by scholars such as Mertha (2024), Cheng and Zeng (2023), and Jones and Hameiri (2021)

The origins of FA can be found in Lieberthal and Oksenberg's seminal study published in 1988, *Policy Making in China: Leaders, Structures and Processes*, which provides a comprehensive examination of the Chinese policymaking apparatus. Lieberthal and Oksenberg argue that while strong centralised authority exists at the pinnacle of the Chinese political system, specifically within the CCP Politburo, below that apex political authority is dispersed and distributed among multiple actors and institutions. This decentralisation of political authority occurs across various dimensions, for example, in the relationship between the central government and local governments and among bureaucratic agencies and ministries within the central party-state. For the Chinese leadership to achieve their objectives under conditions of power fragmentation, they must negotiate and compromise with the numerous competing interests and power centres that wield considerable autonomy and influence within the system. As a result, policymaking in China is often an incremental and protracted process, leading to the dilution or distortion of policies from their original intent and frequently encountering implementation challenges along the way.

The FA model was a departure from previous studies in that it emphasised the importance of bureaucratic structure in determining decision-making and policy outcomes. In contrast, scholars such as Dittmer (1987) and Goldstein (1991) claimed that informal power dynamics, such as factional divisions and power contests within the CCP leadership, offered the most compelling insights into the machinations of the Chinese political system. FA shifted the focus away from elite politics to examining the interorganisational bargaining of formal mid-level bureaucracies. Ultimately the FA model suggests degrees of dysfunction in the Chinese political system; at best the policy process is slow and disjointed, as worst it is paralysed and contradictory. FA also claims that instead of being centralised and driven by the Chinese leadership, policymaking is led by bureaucracies, local governments, state-owned enterprises, and other mid-level actors and institutions within the political system that have accrued significant power. Hence, rather than being top-down and hierarchical, according to FA the flow of political authority in the Chinese political system is middle-up and dispersed horizontally. Mid-level bureaucratic entities often engage in negotiations, bargaining, and competition with each other, leading to policy outcomes that reflect their interests and priorities, which may diverge from the broader national interest or central leadership's key objectives.

Problems with the fragmented authoritarianism model

FA continues to be widely applied by scholars writing on governance in China. This is puzzling given the three —decades of significant political and economic reforms in

China since the model was first proposed. While it is true that there was an era of decentralisation in China which lasted from 1978 to 1993 (referred to as the ‘first reform period’ by Naughton (2008, 91–135)), there have been concerted efforts to recentralise political authority since roughly 1994 (Yang and Sheng 2021, 40–56). The Tiananmen Square events in 1989 and the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 catalysed reforms aimed at reconsolidating central political authority. Recentralisation gained further momentum under Xi’s leadership not only in terms of shifting power away from local governments and back to the central government, but also away from state institutions and back to the CCP, consolidating what has been called ‘party-centric governance’ (Taylor 2022). Hence, in a contemporary policy setting, FA overstates decentralisation in the Chinese political system and the weakness of the central party-state.

Importantly, FA underestimates the enduring and pervasive influence of the CCP, the most important and powerful institution in the Chinese political system, and the primary counterbalance to political fragmentation. FA’s narrow focus on state bureaucracy and state-owned enterprises (with the exception of Mertha’s (2009) ‘fragmented authoritarianism 2.0’, which includes private actors) fails to capture the countervailing and centralising forces within the party-state that hold the system together and make it work. The Party may appear to be less active than it is in reality due to the fact that it is a secretive and opaque entity, especially at the highest levels. This makes it difficult to study due to the need to infer from policy implementation, speeches, and publications rather than having documentary evidence (Jones and Hameiri 2021, 63). However, such lack of transparency does not mean that the Party’s internal decision-making processes are not central to governance in China.

As a model, FA presents a static and reductive view of governance, since it is not equipped to explain institutional evolution, adaptation, and change. While it may offer insights into the compartmentalised nature of authority in specific contexts, it fails to capture the adaptability and resilience of governance structures. FA also does not comprehend the nuanced synthesis of top-down directives with bottom —and middle-up feedback, which is testament to the adaptive capacity of the Chinese state and its capacity to learn and respond through feedback and observation. This adaptive capacity for learning and innovation occurs in response to internal (institutional, ideological, and societal) and external (for example, the demands of globalisation) developments and challenges (Shambaugh 2008). FA does not adequately account for this sophisticated, adaptive, and flexible governing system.

It also does not account for the fact that even during the earlier phases of decentralisation, political authority was not seized away from the centre by other actors (bureaucracies, local governments, state-owned enterprises (SOEs)) in the system but was intentionally delegated downwards and outwards. Hamrin and Zhao (1995, xxvii) offer this critique in stating that the FA model erroneously implied an ‘uncontrolled process’ where mid-level bureaucratic actors have been able to wrest authority from the central party-state. In fact, this was never the case. Power was always shared as a strategy to achieve specific policy objectives and outcomes, but with the caveat that the centre could (and would) reclaim this power if it became necessary, or if the objectives were not being met. Instances of state decentralisation and devolution are better understood as carefully considered, intentional, and strategic and, importantly, can readily be reversed when the need arises.

In the discipline of political science there has been a turn away from the study of elite politics and political parties towards the ‘state’ as comprised of the bureaucracy and technocratic personnel—the East Asian developmental state model is a prime example of this (Brødsgaard and Zheng 2004). Furthermore, from the beginning of the Reform Era (‘reform and opening’, *gaige kaifang*) in the late 1970s through to the end of the Hu Jintao presidency, a more institutionalised, rule-bound, bureaucratic, and technocratic mode of governance was built and maintained, which seemed to indicate that both arbitrary party and personalistic rule had been abandoned (Huang 2004, 32–339). As a result, the CCP in academic literature is often treated as ‘little more than the assumed and elusive source of power behind the state’ (Snape and Wang 2020, 477–502), or as an ‘auxiliary attachment to the state’ (Guo 2020, 441). While the CCP leadership lacks transparency and is not readily accessible to researchers, their rule produces observable effects and outcomes, and increasingly explicit mechanisms through which party power is projected.

This is especially the case in the Xi Jinping era, where the party-state apparatus has been restructured in ways that strengthen the CCP’s position as the preeminent source of political authority in the system (Gore 2023). Some of these changes effectively reverse Deng’s initiatives, notably the nominal separation of party and state organs and functions. A range of structural, legal, and constitutional reforms and amendments have been implemented to enable the recentralization and consolidation of political power within the Party, resulting in the absorption of state institutions into party-led entities (Horsley 2019). Such centralisation and consolidation within the central government has served to defragment many policy sectors and reclaim the authority that had been delegated downwards to local governments. Observers have noted that the era of local government experimentation in economic reforms has effectively ended as officials are increasingly obligated to follow central directives and avoid involvement in political decision-making (Nee and Oppen 2007, 108; The Economist 2018).

Under Xi’s leadership, significant constitutional amendments were also undertaken for the express purpose of elevating CCP power and authority. In addition to the enshrinement of ‘Xi Jinping Thought’, the reinforcement of absolute leadership of the CCP over the military, and the creation of a new Party supervisory body devoted to anti-corruption, an amendment to include support for the BRI was introduced (NPC 2017). This top-down directive places the BRI at the centre of China’s foreign policy and thus further consolidates and centralizes strategic control of the initiative in Beijing. Enshrining the BRI in the constitution raises the stakes and puts even greater pressure on all the actors involved to align their investment decisions with Beijing’s foreign policy and strategic aims.

Suggesting that China’s political system is broadly characterised by FA, when the most compelling cases for its existence were only in certain economic sectors, is also problematic. It has always been the case that FA was much less applicable to the military, propaganda, foreign policy, monetary policy, news-media, political doctrine and ideological matters, cybersecurity, internet governance, and a range of strategic industries including nuclear energy and aerospace. All of these have maintained a more centralised decision-making and oversight apparatus where the flow of authority is decidedly top-down (Lieberthal and Lampton 1992; Zhao 1995). This limited applicability of FA has not been

widely acknowledged, with the general assumption being that the Chinese political system is fragmented and decentralised across the board, including in the implementation of foreign policy. For instance, Hameiri and Jones (2016, 73) claim that ‘fragmented and decentralised state apparatuses and quasi-market actors are increasingly pursuing their own independent interests and agendas overseas, generating conflict-ridden, incoherent policy output, often mistakenly interpreted as “grand strategy”’. This assumption does not accord well with reality: the Chinese state has shown itself to be relatively effective and coherent over the past four decades—as we will demonstrate in the remainder of this paper.

Flexible authoritarianism

Rather than *fragmented* authoritarianism, we posit that China’s governance system can be characterised as *flexible* authoritarianism. Instead of policy formation typically arising from mid-level actors and bureaucratic institutions, we suggest that it is overwhelmingly guided and formed by the party leadership in order to advance China’s national security goals and long-term strategy. While it is certainly true that many foreign policy directives, for example, within the framework of the BRI, appear at first sight to be vague, over-ambitious, and difficult to interpret (Brown 2015; Kuhrt 2015, 21–3), the aim of this paper is to show that this is deliberate, the intention being to create a broad envelope for the pragmatic implementation of policy in the field (Garlick 2024). Mid-level actors, rather than openly contesting and negotiating policy, can be seen under usual circumstances to be flexibly interpreting and implementing top-down directives as conduits of overall strategy, but with a considerable degree of autonomy. When agents of the state go beyond the (unwritten but tacitly understood) bounds of the permissible—for instance, by engaging in corrupt practices—they are brought forcibly back into line or replaced by others.

Leading sinologist David Shambaugh (2008) has characterised China’s authoritarian governance style as ‘atrophy and adaptation’. Above all, his book demonstrates that the Chinese government reacted to the events of 1989 by attempting to ensure, above all, that what it saw as the failure of the Soviet Union to maintain national unity would not occur in China. The Party did this by seeking to counter the fragmentation that had occurred in the reform period from 1979 to 1993 through a recentralization of governance mechanisms, concentration of power in the hands of Party members, and by developing policies that would serve four overarching and closely connected goals. Chief among these four goals, of course, was the survival of the CCP. The second priority was the maintenance of national unity and the avoidance of fragmentation along the lines experienced in the first half of the twentieth century. A third key priority was what came to be called China’s ‘comprehensive national security’, comprising military, energy, and economic security goals (Heath 2016). The fourth and final goal was to sustain long-term economic growth in order to build China’s national power and to earn support from the majority of the population.

These four key goals became the cornerstones of Chinese foreign policy in the post-Tiananmen era and remain key priorities under Xi. All Chinese foreign policy is designed to achieve these overarching goals. The specifics of how these goals will be reached is

intended to be flexible, adjusting to circumstances as needs demand. Thus, there is latitude for actors to decide how to implement goals, as long as such implementation remains within certain boundaries. Accordingly, although the goals and boundaries of policy have not been given a written form, if an actor is seen to have gone beyond what is expected, particularly if it has taken policy implementation in an unintended direction, it will be reined in. Fragmented ad hoc policymaking on the ground, tolerated if it does not threaten the overarching policy goals, is permitted in areas of detail and daily operation; but it is not allowed to supersede party-centric governance and national strategy.

In short, the Chinese approach to governance, especially under Xi, does not have the characteristics of FA and instead can be designated *flexible authoritarianism*. To demonstrate this, in the next section we present evidence from selected areas of Chinese foreign policy in the Xi Jinping era, including economic diplomacy in the Czech Republic, Chinese strategy in the South China Sea, and energy policy.

Evidence for flexible authoritarianism

In this section, we investigate the implementation of Chinese foreign policy during the period of Xi's presidency. Using an evidence-based, narrative approach, we present cases that are typically explained in the literature through the application of an FA lens, instead providing an alternative assessment to show that Chinese foreign policy emerges from flexible rather than fragmented authoritarianism.

Czech-China relations: the case of CEFC

A revealing example of China's flexible authoritarianism foreign policy model is the case of Chinese economic diplomacy in the Czech Republic. In this case, a private company (CEFC) became the de facto agent of the Chinese state, with a high degree of flexibility to develop partnerships and invest as it saw fit. In 2016, a Chinese investment package for Czechia was put together, with CEFC acting as both the state's agent and as a private investor. From the Chinese state's perspective, the aim of the investments was to cultivate both business ties and political influence for China in Czechia. This was done under the overarching framework of President Xi Jinping's BRI, launched in 2013, of which Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) was viewed as a key region on the route to Western Europe (Garlick 2020). To assist with cultivating improved ties with the CEE region, the so-called '16 + 1' (later '17 + 1' with the addition of Greece) cooperation framework had already been launched in 2012. The Czech Republic was seen by the Xi administration as one of the key members of this new, Chinese-led framework (China is the '+1' in the equation). Hence, the Chinese government saw the investment package, guided by CEFC but also involving Chinese state actors, as a golden opportunity to implement its aims in Czechia (Fürst 2018).

In this context, in 2015 the CEO of CEFC, Ye Jianming, was appointed as a special advisor to the Czech president, Miloš Zeman, ahead of a visit by President Xi Jinping in 2016 at the invitation of the Czech president (Zelenka 2019). During Xi's visit, thirty memoranda and business agreements were signed, among which CEFC was the leading agent and investor. The financing of some of the agreements was to come

from several Chinese banks, including the China Development Bank. However, CEFC took responsibility for financing the investments in which it was the primary signatory (Menzelová 2017).

However, when the company failed to meet its financial obligations amid accusations of corruption, the Chinese government made a decision to replace it with the state-owned company CITIC (Garlick 2019, 439). In effect, CEFC's actions had departed from the bounds of the permissible and the state was forced to intervene, resolving the resultant principal-agent problem from the top down. The flexible authoritarianism model provides a good explanation of this case, because a single actor was given official permission to act relatively flexibly as the agent of the state but its actions failed to fulfil its remit and it was replaced. Thus, flexible authoritarianism provides a more accurate explanation of Chinese foreign policy implementation in the era of the BRI than fragmentation.

Examining the details of the case in more detail is instructive. After the collapse of communism in CEE in 1989, Czech-China relations, which had anyway been minimal due to the Sino-Soviet split, became even colder due to Czech President Havel's attempts to court Taiwan (Tubilewicz 2007, 54–9). This state of affairs continued even after Czechia joined the EU in 2004. However, relations began to warm up after the creation of the 16 + 1 platform for cooperation between China and CEE, especially after a visit by President Zeman to Beijing in 2015 (Fürst 2018, 127). As the Chinese state began to promote the BRI, a role emerged for agents to promote China's interests in the CEE region. In Czechia, CEFC pushed itself forward into that role, negotiating investment deals which were endorsed by President Xi Jinping personally during a visit to Prague in 2016. Investments signed during 2015 and 2016 included stakes in an engineering and metallurgical company, two media companies, and a finance group (Menzelová 2017).

However, CEFC's actions soon began to appear less than ideal for the flexible role of agent of the state it had been granted. When CEFC failed to follow through on some of its share purchases, disgruntlement began to emerge on the Czech side (Menzelová 2017). Soon after, accusations of bribery by company officials in Africa emerged, damaging CEFC's image further. The CEO of the company, Ye Jianming, was detained in China, while the CFO, Patrick Ho, was arrested in the U.S. (Garlick 2019, 444; Ng and Yu 2018). A decision was taken for CITIC, a state-owned enterprise (SOE), to take over CEFC's portfolio of Czech investments (Reuters 2018).

In this case, a situation emerged in which an agent which had been given a degree of autonomy to make investments promoting both its own and the state's interests strayed beyond the bounds of the permissible. CEFC failed to meet its financial obligations, one of its officials was publicly accused of corruption, and China's image in the Czech Republic and around the world was tarnished as reports emerged in the media (Barboza, Santora, and Stevenson 2018). The situation was resolved by the deployment of an SOE at the behest of the central government, re-establishing state oversight and avoiding fragmentation. In this case, the fact that emergency intervention from the centre was required reveals the initial use of the flexible authoritarianism model, with an actor given a degree of leeway to guide investments as part of an overall strategy of promoting the Chinese state's interests.

The South China Sea

A frequently mentioned example of supposed fragmentation in Chinese foreign policy is Beijing's strategy towards the South China Sea (SCS). Jones and Hameiri (2021, 101–7) claim that there is no coherent strategy since policy arises on the hoof from contestation between a range of actors including the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), the People's Liberation Army Navy (PLAN), coastguards, and even the provincial government of Hainan Island. Jakobson and Manuel (2016) offer a milder formulation, suggesting that '... maritime security actors involved in the South China Sea are said to have greater freedom than those involved in the East China Sea because senior leaders are more attentive to relations with Japan than to smaller Southeast Asian nations'. Such analyses suggest that actors such as the PLAN and the MFA have a degree of autonomy and flexibility in decision-making in areas of detail, but the degree of overall coordination and strategy is disputed.

We posit that there is a remarkable degree of consistency and long-term strategy to Chinese operations in the SCS in the BRI era. This is indicative of agents of the state adhering to a coherent overall strategy even as they make decisions on the hoof in areas of detail, leading to the appearance of a degree of inconsistency in the implementation of policy. Yamaguchi (2016, 30) shows that coordination between Chinese actors in the SCS has been improving under the Xi administration:

China's maritime actors may be in competition, but not to an extent that could disrupt China's overall strategy. At least they are working under the broad policy direction of the CCP, and it is therefore the CCP leadership that is pushing the tough policy line in the SCS.

Rather than fragmentation or lack of coherent strategy, this is suggestive of a government setting broad and consistent policy goals within which actors are allowed a degree of leeway. As Fravel (2018, 44–5) explains, this pertains also to military affairs, since

despite subordination to the party, the military is granted substantial autonomy within the realm of military affairs so that it has sufficient freedom to perform the tasks that the party requires. Therefore, top officers in a party-army are positioned to initiate the process of strategic change more than civilian members of the party leadership. Yet because military leaders themselves are also senior party members, they will formulate new strategies consistent with the party's broader political goals, minimizing differences with party leaders.

Coordination is especially important given the strategic importance of the SCS for Chinese shipping and oil imports (Fravel 2011, 296). Logically, it is hardly likely that the central government would allow its policy in such a critically strategic region to spiral out of control amidst contestation of decision-making between the army, provincial governments and the foreign ministry. Hence, we suggest that the flexible authoritarianism model is a better depiction of China's activity in the SCS than the idea that there is fragmentation between a range of actors and an implied lack of coordination and strategy.

A prime example of coherent strategy is the terraforming of seven islands which took place over a relatively short period of time in 2014 and 2015. Construction operations involved the use of a large number of vessels including dredgers which pumped sand and other material from the seabed onto the rocks, reefs, and atolls which up until that point had constituted China's previously uninhabitable possessions. Runways and

military installations were built on the islands (Storey 2015). Construction continued on each of the seven islands during this period until all installations were complete and the seven islands were manned by personnel. At no point in this process was there any evidence of public contestation from any actors involved or from any Chinese government organs. It can thus be concluded, without reasonable doubt, that the construction of the islands and the installations upon them was coordinated from the highest level of the Chinese government as a long-term strategy designed to expand China's interests and power base in the SCS. Of course, it is possible that the military thought up this strategy; but certainly, government and army were on the same page in terms of developing, endorsing and implementing it. Logically, such coordinated activity by a large number of actors over a relatively short period could not have been achieved without everybody being on the same page and without the central government being the linchpin of overall decision-making in close coordination with the military (Yamaguchi 2016).

The inference that there must be backroom policy and strategy coordination from on high, even in the absence of clear documentary evidence, also accounts for the fact that there has been no forced boarding of vessels by the Chinese Coastguard (CCG) since its formation in 2013 (Morris 2019, 86). Nor have there been any deaths or significant violence apart from damage to ships amidst numerous incidents of assertive action by the CCG. The fact that the CCG has abstained from violence against personnel indicates that it has received broad policy parameters. Even if one takes the assertion by Jones and Hameiri (2021, 115) that the CCG is prone to 'internal chaos' at face value, it is clear that even when policy is implemented ad hoc by vessel commanders, these agents of the state continue to operate according to overarching policy guidelines.

Jones and Hameiri (2021) also suggest that the Chinese insistence on claiming almost the entire territory of the SCS via the 'nine-dash line' is a product of fragmented foreign policy. Their examples demonstrate that this may have been the case pre-Xi administration, or in the early days after Xi assumed control; but in the present era there is no contestation between Chinese actors concerning the validity of the Chinese claim over the entire SCS. At the broadest level, the nine —(or ten-) dash line is an established part of Chinese foreign policy in the region to which all interested Chinese actors unwaveringly adhere. This demonstrates that the policy must be coordinated from the centre, emanating from the central government, even though military officers are responsible for formulating and implementing specific strategies.

Similarly, Jones and Hameiri (2021, 72–120) correctly point out that there was a degree of contestation of SCS policy between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA) and subordinate bodies from the 1990s up to 2014, soon after Xi Jinping was installed as leader. However, they fail to give enough weight to the following point: that although there was fragmentation in SCS policy during this period, decision-making has been recentralized over the course of the Xi presidency. Chinese foreign policy is now formulated in the Politburo rather than the MFA, via the Central Foreign Affairs Commission (Legarda 2018). This body, which previously had been called the Central Foreign Affairs Leading Small Group (LSG), was put in direct charge of maritime affairs in 2018, cementing central leadership oversight of SCS policy (Gore 2023). Since 2018, it has been difficult to find much evidence of 'fragmentation' in China's approach to the SCS.

Another point worth making is that there may be an alternative explanation for what Jones and Hameiri (2021, 76) interpret as China's inconsistent actions in the SCS, 'with

conflict escalating and de-escalating, often within the space of a year' and 'an almost incomprehensible level of unpredictability': as military strategy rather than fragmentation. From a strategic perspective, an army attempting to gain and maintain a degree of control of an objective—especially one contested by as many actors as the SCS—would be well-advised *not* to do it in a completely predictable or transparent manner. Instead, it would be strategically useful to unsettle and catch the enemy off-guard by using an element of surprise, accompanied by a withholding of clear information. Indeed, writing in the journal *US Army War College Quarterly: Parameters*, military analyst Timothy Thomas (2014) points out that People's Liberation Army (PLA) officers have traditionally been taught to lean heavily on strategies of surprise and uncertainty to confuse enemies and gain strategic advantages (Thomas 2014, 45–6). This is especially the case in conditions where they may be at a material disadvantage, for instance in relation to superior U.S. military and naval technology. Citing retired Lieutenant General Li Jijun, formerly Deputy Commandant of the Chinese Academy of Military Sciences, Thomas demonstrates that '[a]cting in an irregular way and the use of uncertainties are "a conscious act of using strategems"' (Thomas 2014, 46, citing Li 2006). Further, '[t]he PLA's lack of transparency is a means of deterrence, since it becomes ambiguous and unpredictable for potential foes' (Thomas 2014, 46). In this interpretation, unexplained rapid and repeated escalation and de-escalation of tensions at irregular intervals via assertive military interventions followed by periods of apparent inactivity would represent a much better explanation of China's 'consistent inconsistency' than fragmentation (Santicola 2014).

Contestation by the military is also being rapidly suppressed as Xi reasserts Party control over the PLA. Hameiri and Jones (2016, 87) are right that the Chinese military has historically been a source of fragmentation in foreign policy implementation. However, this tendency has clearly been noted by the Xi administration and countermeasures have been taken to reimplement central control and reduce fragmentation. The process of reassertion of central governance began early in Xi's presidency, in 2014, with the twin aims of installing a pro-Xi support base in the PLA and modernising the military to prepare it for modern warfare (McCauley 2015). Xi has consistently emphasised the need for 'integrated national strategies and strategic capabilities', in order to 'consolidate and boost unity between the military and the government and between the military and the people' (Xi quoted in Ding and Tang 2023, 19–20). Hence, Xi replaced key personnel in both the PLA and the defence ministry in 2023 and early 2024, ostensibly due to accusations of corruption. This provides evidence of efforts to consolidate and enforce party-centric governance with regard to national security and the military (Lin 2024, 6–10). Increasingly, the military is run by the Party and does not take decisions or implement actions which run counter to central policy, although it clearly has a considerable degree of flexibility and autonomy concerning the implementation of policy in the field.

Energy policy and security

One major area that has long been of interest to China studies and foreign policy scholars alike, is China's energy policy and security. There is a strong tendency to claim that Chinese national oil companies (NOCs) are largely autonomous, tend to act in their

own interests, and make deals on the fly, without consulting the central government (Downs 2008; Hameiri and Jones 2016, 87; Houser 2008; Kong 2010). Through such claims, scholars intend to show evidence of fragmentation in Chinese foreign policy and that the government is forced to react to deals being struck by its NOCs rather than guiding them strategically. However, there is a wealth of evidence to suggest that Chinese energy policy overseas is relatively coordinated and in tune with overall foreign policy, serving the key goal of promoting China's energy security (Lee 2012; Taylor 2014). This is seen by the government as crucial to China's comprehensive national security and therefore cannot be left to completely ad hoc decision-making that might contradict this goal. On the other hand, it is undoubtedly true that actors are given considerable flexibility to make decisions—as long as these remain within prescribed parameters. The central government builds in the assumption that NOCs will pursue profit. However, it is not permissible for individual and corporate interests to co-opt or damage the interests of the Chinese state. Accordingly, as we will demonstrate, individuals who are seen to have acted counter to national interests are weeded out and punished as the state reasserts its control and seeks to reduce fragmentation.

China's NOCs (China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC), Sinopec, and China National Offshore Oil Corporation (CNOOC)) are central to China's energy policy and security agenda. While they are internationally competitive companies that enjoy a high degree of operational autonomy, especially in day-to-day management and business operations, their strategic direction is broadly dictated by Beijing. High-level strategic control is maintained primarily through the CCP's influence over personnel appointments at the senior executive level and the presence of embedded party committees within these companies, along with state financing, ownership rights and oversight by state regulators (notably the State-Owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission (SASAC) of the State Council), which provide the central government with the necessary leverage to guide the investment decisions and strategic directions of the NOCs. These companies are also legally obligated to integrate the relevant objectives of Five-Year Plans and other national development plans and strategies into their business plans.

The personnel appointment system is particularly important for understanding both the ways in which the Chinese state influences the strategic direction of the NOCs and how the corporate governance of SOEs in China differs significantly from Western ideas about corporate governance. This system, also known as the nomenklatura system, is administered through the Central Organization Department (COD). Senior executives in China's SOEs are typically drawn from the state bureaucracy and CCP (Taylor 2014, 161–6). This reflects the closely intertwined relationship between the government and SOEs in China, where leadership roles encompass both managerial and political expertise; a necessary combination for ensuring the alignment of corporate objectives with national strategies and policies. It is not unusual for executives and chairmen to take up high-level government appointments following their company tenure. For example, Su Shulin, former chairman of Sinopec, went on to become Governor of Fujian Province (Xinhua 2018). This provides further incentive for SOE company executives to balance corporate autonomy with the advancement of national policy objectives. In the case of the NOCs, these objectives include energy security and also aspects of environmental policy and broader economic policy.

To weed out corruption and political rivals and consolidate the Party's authority over the oil sector, the 'petro purge' began shortly after Xi Jinping came to power. During this purge several key figures in the oil industry were investigated or charged with corruption. One of the most notable purgees was Zhou Yongkang, former member of the Politburo Standing Committee, former head of China's internal security services, former chief executive of CNPC, and a well-known political adversary of Xi (Taylor 2021, 904). A member of China's 'petroleum gang' throughout the 1990s and 2000s, Zhou was an especially influential oil industry figure, and in 2015 was sentenced to life in prison for bribery, abuse of power, and intentionally disclosing national secrets (Aredy 2015). By removing powerful figures who might have had the ability to operate with a degree of autonomy or resist central directives, Xi, and the CCP more broadly, aim to ensure that the strategic direction of the oil industry is closely aligned with the goals and interests of the party-state. Importantly, through its anti-corruption campaign the party leadership also demonstrated its capacity to disrupt and reorient an entire sector by eliminating the most influential players. Awareness of these domestic oil industry dynamics is key to understanding the international behaviour of the NOCs and the ways in which their strategic direction is influenced by Beijing.

The overseas oil deals of China's NOCs also receive significant foreign policy and diplomatic support, indicating a high degree of coordination, rather than fragmentation, among Chinese government bureaucracies and between the Chinese government and the NOCs. Zhang and Chen's interviews of officials in the MFA involved in Brazilian oil deals provide interesting insights into the inner workings of Chinese foreign policy in the area of energy imports (Zhang and Chen 2021). According to one of their anonymous interviewees, '... since political and strategic cooperation is the overriding priority in the Chinese—Brazilian partnership, any proposition for or directive on economic cooperation is always from the top down—and hence decision-making is fairly centralised' (Zhang and Chen 2021, 356). The same official and two others also lamented their lack of involvement in decision-making processes. According to these officials,

It is the top leaders from both sides who are at the core of the institutional hierarchy, and thus with limited participation by the ministers, vice-ministers, and department heads. Task groups are confined more to a technical role in the process. To more closely involve the rank and file in the decision-making process has, in fact, been a critical issue that the Brazilian side keeps raising with their Chinese counterparts. (Zhang and Chen 2021, 356)

This top-down decision-making process is indicative of the CCP's emphasis on the vital strategic importance of oil imports for China's economy. As a result, since Brazil's state-owned oil company Petrobras signed an export contract with China's NOC Sinopec in 2006, Brazil has become China's fifth largest supplier of crude. By 2019, 63 per cent of Brazil's oil exports were directed to China, constituting 8 per cent of China's total oil imports (Barbosa 2021, 368). China's single-minded focus on obtaining oil imports from Brazil supports the assertion that possible fragmentation in decision-making has been effectively reduced to a minimum while permitting some autonomy to actors in areas of detail (Moura 2023).

Conclusion

The evidence presented in this paper is intended to support the assertion that China's implementation of foreign policy under Xi Jinping is flexible and party-centric rather than fragmented. A degree of vagueness in overall policy is deliberate, leaving space for local actors to make adjustments within the loosely defined boundaries. However, overstepping the unwritten bounds of the permissible—in effect, acting against what the central administration sees as China's and the Party's vital national security goals—invariably produces a reaction from the centre. Where actors seem to overstep the mark, but the Xi administration does not perceive such action as affecting national security goals, it may turn a blind eye. This action/non-action dichotomy, depending on circumstances, reflects a consistent pragmatic pattern in both Chinese domestic and foreign policy.

Thus, what in the eyes of some observers appears to be inconsistency, incoherence, lack of coordination, and lack of strategy is in fact a misinterpretation of the Xi administration's approach to achieving broad foreign policy goals. These include maintaining China's overall economic growth trajectory, supporting the Party's control of the PRC, and ruthlessly suppressing any and all threats to national unity. In the foreign policy sphere, the administration expects commercial and diplomatic actors to contribute to national growth and unity by striking deals to secure energy, generate influence, and boost trade. How they do this is up to them to a certain extent, as long as they do not step outside the unwritten bounds of the permissible—for instance by failing to fulfil promised investments, by being conspicuously corrupt, or by challenging the rule of the Party.

There is no doubt that there has been a tendency to fragmentation in terms of foreign policy implementation. It is inevitable that principal-agent problems, in which the agent takes action to suit its own interests rather than those of the principal, will occur. Yet it is also noticeable that when fragmentation occurs due to a Chinese actor going beyond the bounds of what the Xi administration sees as permissible, action to reverse this tendency and re-establish control occurs. As already noted, Chinese foreign policy combines flexibility (adapting to changing circumstances) and party-centric authoritarianism (in reasserting top-down governance when necessary).

In the end, since China like any other large nation-state is subject to huge internal and external pressures, so that managing such an unwieldy entity is akin to trying to juggle a large number of balls without dropping any of them, a degree of fragmentation will always be evident. Inevitably, some of the balls will drop to the ground. Yet it is remarkable, especially under Xi's tightening regime, how few balls are dropped and how consistent and unified a foreign policy actor the party-centric PRC manages to be. Indeed, China is arguably more consistent and strategic in its foreign policy implementation than most Western countries, most notably the USA (Garlick 2024). While the US has shifted direction over the last two decades, sometimes drastically, China, for the most part, has stuck to and achieved its broad long-term foreign policy goals. These goals include gaining a greater degree of control in the SCS, ensuring China's energy security, and persuading an increasing number of countries in the global South to switch their allegiance from Taiwan to the PRC (Garlick and Qin 2024). Realising that it is not possible to monitor every detail of every transaction in every region and country of the world, the central

administration has necessarily delegated some responsibility to its agents in areas of detail—as long as they stick within the unwritten bounds of the permissible and work towards what the Party sees as comprehensive national security goals. This flexible, pragmatic approach has given the PRC a remarkably resilient and consistent overall direction, casting doubt on the notion that it is not possible for China to pursue long-term strategic goals due to supposed fragmentation in the system.

The flexible authoritarianism model, while used in this article to analyse Chinese foreign policy, also represents a contribution to the literature on authoritarianism more broadly. Building on Schwenck (2024), it offers an alternative to dichotomous representations of autocracy as being either completely centralised or fragmented. Instead, flexible authoritarianism conceives authoritarianism as a governance model capable of existing along a spectrum between the two, containing elements of both centralised consolidation of power and a considerable degree of autonomy for agents of the state. In other words, flexible authoritarianism provides conceptual space for understanding authoritarian regimes such as China which seek to maintain power by allowing actors to pursue profit and self-interest as long as doing so promotes the broad strategic goals of the state.

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